

The Cute Look: Baby-Schema Effects in Product Design

Visual Key Stimuli in Car Fronts and Human Faces

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Abstract: According to evolutionary theory, some visual key stimuli such as the baby-schema (“Kindchenschema”) automatically elicit strong positive responses in consumers (e.g., affection and approach behavior). Previous studies have suggested that consumers perceive and process car fronts analog to human faces. However, it is not known how consumers respond on an affective level to such biologically relevant patterns when they are present in artifacts. In two experiments, we examined whether people would provide similar cuteness ratings to pictures of car fronts and faces, which were manipulated according to the baby-schema. Our results showed that people were able to detect the baby-schema in car fronts. Further, people’s cuteness ratings of car fronts, although generally lower, were comparable to their cuteness ratings of human faces. Hence, visual key stimuli might be powerful product design features to create affect-laden product designs.

Key words: *Baby-schema, anthropomorphism, cuteness perception, evolutionary theory.*

1 Introduction

Companies profit greatly when consumers fall in love with their products on the first sight. In marketing and product development, it is well known that as the technical quality of consumer products becomes similar, the emotional value of products gains in importance [1, 2, 3]. Thus, the visual appearance of a product is an important marketing tool to appeal to consumers’ emotions, and to elicit spontaneous affective responses such as “How beautiful!” or “How cute!”. A well-established trend in product design is the creation of forms that somehow resemble humans, which is reflected, for example, by a car designer’s concern for the “face” of a car [4, 5]. Product designers therefore exploit an innate human trait already known to psychologists and anthropologists: due to the evolutionary value of human forms, consumers are highly sensitive and attracted to them [6]. Marketing and design professionals’ assumptions on what attracts consumers may be based intuitively on such evolutionary principles (e.g., consumers’ preferences are shaped by innate motives and needs) [7]. However, the effects of such forms on product design appreciation have not been investigated systematically.

To address the needs and preferences of consumers, marketing and design professionals need behavioral theories. Surprisingly, evolutionary theory, which could be useful for marketing, consumer research, and product

development [8], has been neglected. To date, only a few researchers have applied an evolutionary psychological approach to understanding consumer behavior [9]. Evolutionary psychology explains human behavior in terms of innate perceptual, cognitive and/or motivational mechanisms that are assumed to have evolved through natural selection as adaptations to ancestral conditions [10].

For product design research and application, understanding innate *perceptual* processes is particularly compelling. In the present research, we investigated one type of innate perceptual process, that is spontaneous responses to visual key stimuli (or visual releasers [11]). We study the baby-schema (“Kindchenschema”), which was first described by Lorenz [12] as a set of physical features usually present in infant faces. The features of the baby-schema elicit spontaneous cuteness perceptions in adults, which are important triggers of positive emotional responses to infants. Therefore, consumers’ responses to visual key stimuli such as the baby-schema are an interesting research topic with regard to the relationship between product design and emotions.

In summary, this paper has two intentions: to theoretically apply an evolutionary psychology framework to product design, and to show its relevance for understanding product appreciation; and to present two empirical studies in which we systematically examined the relevance of specific evolutionarily-relevant physical features to product design. The studies examined how consumers respond affectively to visual key stimuli (i.e., the baby-schema) that are presented in non-humans, that is consumer products.

1.1 Human Evolution and Visual Key Stimuli: The Baby-Schema

From Biology and Psychology it is known that the presence of particular stimuli, so called *key stimuli*, automatically triggers innate cognitive, affective or motivational responses in individuals perceiving these stimuli (e.g., Zebrowitz, p. 68 [16]). Key stimuli are usually – but not always – visual (e.g., a special animal coat pattern formation or a specific body movement to attract potential mates). Thus, they are a very interesting starting point when investigating the significance of human evolution for product design appreciation. People’s automatic responses to key stimuli are adaptive since they have developed during human evolution to guarantee one’s own and the kin’s survival and reproduction. Even though modern consumers’ environments are obviously different from the environments where these adaptive mechanisms evolved, human preferences and behaviors are still shaped by these mechanisms. This has been shown for different domains of everyday life such as mating [13], food choice [14] and even aesthetic preferences [15].

Undoubtedly, babies elicit spontaneous favorable responses in most perceivers [16]. The initial reaction to infants is an approach behavior such as smiling [17, 18, 19], and people prefer pictures of infants over pictures of adults [20, 21, 22]. Lorenz [12] stated that babies are approached positively because their physical appearance triggers affection and nurturing in people, and that this promotes parental caretaking, and consequently, offspring survival. There is high agreement regarding the physical features that comprise the baby-schema: round face, large eyes, small nose and mouth, thick lips, and small chin - to name a few [23-28] (for a review of the features, see Zebrowitz, [16], pp. 68-78). In accordance with Lorenz’ assumptions, previous studies have shown that baby-schema features are correlated with perceived infant cuteness [17] and adults’ motivation for caretaking [25, 29]: infants with more “babyish” facial features (e.g., larger eyes, smaller nose) were perceived as cuter and elicited stronger motivation in adults for caretaking.

Zebrowitz [16] (p. 78) and others suggest the baby-schema to be an abstract visual pattern which is more than the appearance quality of a specific organism, hence, it may characterize various organisms. Equally, Lorenz [12] postulated that these features elicit positive responses even when they are present in non-humans. In line with this assertion, Zebrowitz [16] (p. 78) and others found that humans are not only sensitive to baby-schema features found in infant faces, but also to those found in members of other species. Humans respond positively to infant animals [30], cute cartoon characters or dolls [31], and baby-faced adults. Concerning the latter, there is a lot of evidence showing that people are able to judge the babyfacedness of human faces of *various* ages [32]. Zebrowitz [33] stated that the similarities in responses to babies and to faces that resemble babies are due to an overgeneralization of the evolutionarily adaptive response of identifying babies (*baby-face overgeneralization hypothesis*).

Regarding the high affective value of the baby-schema in the context of product design research and application, the following question arises: are the features of the baby-schema so resilient that they can be seen even in non-living things such as design products? If consumers respond to cute design products as they would respond to cute living organisms, this might have important implications for product design appreciation.

1.2 Previous Research on Face-like Product Designs

Up to now, researchers who have considered the impact of design on product evaluations focused on general descriptive product attributes such as color and shape. For example, Seva, Been-Lirn Duh, and Helander [34], investigated different mobile phone designs by addressing design attributes such color, display size and shapes of navigation buttons. Such product category-specific, exploratory approaches are interesting when one aims to create design guidelines for one specific product category. Results from such investigations, however, lack generalizability because they are specific to one product category. In contrast, applying an evolutionary psychology framework (i.e., the theory of the baby-schema) allows the specification of the values of features that could positively affect consumer perceptions across different product categories: for example, round shapes should be perceived as cuter than square shapes. In this regard, Khalid and Helander [3] demanded that “an explicit requirement of emotional design is that it should be theoretically driven and empirically grounded (...)” (p. 198). One exception to the rather exploratory design research approaches is the upcoming research on human-like forms in product design based on the theory of anthropomorphism (i.e., seeing non-humans as humans [6]). Although there are many examples for human-like designed products (for an overview see for example DiSalvo and Gemperle [35]), systematic research regarding such anthropomorphic product forms is still scarce, but increasing [36-38]. As we address the effects of baby-schema features on design appreciation, our research is mainly based on previous studies that have dealt with face-like product designs. Cars are often mentioned in discussions of face-like forms in product design. It has been suggested that a car’s front is perceived and processed similarly to a human face. So, Windhager et al. [5] and Erk et al. [39] have provided evidence that consumers are able to assign facial features to components of car fronts without much effort. For example, Windhager et al. [5] investigated people’s eye movement patterns when comparing car fronts with human faces, and found that a car’s headlights are considered as eyes, the grille as the nose, and the air intake or the grille as the mouth. Miesler, Landwehr, Herrmann and McGill [38] revealed that due to the car front’s face-like physical features, presenting a car shown in front view automatically activates a human face schema in the consumer’s mind, whereas presenting a car shown from side view does not. In another study, Windhager et al.

[40] found evidence that car fronts are interpreted as faces, and that people draw the same inferences from car fronts as from faces (e.g., concerning perceived sex, or maturity).

Thus, biologically-related forms, such as those that are face-like, might be detected in artifacts. However, such detection would not automatically imply that the face-like forms would also produce product-related emotions (e.g., by eliciting affection). For example, seeing faces in clouds does not necessarily change one's attitude towards clouds. Thus, from a designer's perspective, both feature detection and affective responses to such features are interesting. Aggarwal and McGill [36] have already demonstrated that products with physical features that are congruent with a human schema are liked more than products with physical features that are incongruent. However, the affective responses found in their study (i.e., liking) were rather due to a cognitive process (i.e., successful cognitive match between a product's appearance and a mental schema) than to specific affect-laden features of the product.

In the present project, we provide support for the assumption that face-like features in car fronts are processed analog to human faces. Moreover, we investigate whether such biologically-relevant patterns have an effect on consumers' affective responses to products. Specifically, we examine a special face schema that is known to be highly affect-laden: the baby-schema. Thus, we tap into the evolutionary perspective of design appreciation by addressing the question of whether people are sensitive to visual key stimuli in artifacts (as assumed intuitively by designers and marketers). If this is the case, people should perceive cuteness similarly in artifacts and human faces. The perception of cuteness has a strong emotional connotation, because as cited above objects which are perceived as cute by consumers elicit strong positive emotions and emotion-related behaviors such as spontaneous smiling. Therefore to examine cuteness perceptions in consumers could inform the development of emotional product designs which appeal to the consumers' emotions on the first sight.

2 Methods

2.1 Hypotheses

We tested the effects of baby-schema features on the perception of cuteness. We used images of car fronts that were supposed to resemble human faces. Importantly, we expected that car fronts with local features that were manipulated according to the baby-schema (e.g., larger headlights, smaller grilles), would be perceived as cuter than non-manipulated car fronts (hypothesis 1). In comparing car fronts with human faces, we predicted that the detection of a baby-schema would elicit cuteness perceptions in both stimuli categories. However, we expected the artificial stimuli to induce weaker cuteness responses than the faces. That is why we assumed that people would be more sensitive to baby-schema cues in faces as compared to car fronts (hypothesis 2).

2.2 Stimuli

As described above, various features could affect the babyish appearance (the "cuteness") of human faces. Two restrictions determined which features we used to manipulate the babyfacedness of both car fronts and human faces. First, as in previous studies [5, 38-40], we selected facial features that clearly corresponded to the features of a car front (e.g., the car's headlights as human eyes). Second, we selected features that had been shown to strongly affect perceived cuteness. Thus, we selected car fronts' headlights (~ eyes), middle grille (~ nose) and

air intake (~ mouth; see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Car Front Features Selected for Manipulation

To create babyfaced car fronts, we manipulated the sizes of the three features. The original stimuli were monochrome photographs of 16 different cars (picture size: 512×512 pixels) shown in front view. For each of these 16 cars, a babyfaced version was created by enlarging the headlights by 20 % (since babies have proportionally large eyes), shrinking the middle grille by 20 % (since babies have proportionally small noses) and increasing the width of the air intake by 20 % while simultaneously increasing its height by 20 % (since babies have small mouths, but relatively thicker lips than adults). Such feature size manipulations in a range of 10-20 % have been also used by other authors (e.g., [26]). Thus, there were two versions of each car, a non-manipulated basic version and a manipulated babyfaced version (see Figure 2, left side). As nine of the cars belonged to the compact car segment and the remaining six cars to the medium-class segment, we included car shape as an additional factor (since babies have rounder faces than adults). We calculated a roundness index separately for each car using the measurement tool in Adobe Photoshop. Specifically, we measured the height and width of each car (points with maximal distance) and divided height by width to derive the roundness index (index = 1, perfect roundness; index < 1, ellipse). We found that the average roundness index for compact cars was significantly higher (and closer to a perfect circle) than the index for medium-class cars ($M_{\text{roundness compact}} = .85$, $SD = 0.02$; $M_{\text{roundness medium}} = .77$, $SD = 0.02$; $t(14) = -7.69$, $p < .001$). This validated our decision to include shape as an additional factor in our study, even though we did not manipulate it systematically.

To test our second hypothesis, and to validate that the features we chose to manipulate were relevant for cuteness perception, we applied identical manipulations to 16 human faces (8 male and 8 female faces; picture size: 370×555 pixels). The pictures were taken from the Vienna Face Database which contains standardized pictures of male and female students with an age range from 18 to 25 years. A pre-study with 19 participants revealed that size manipulations of 20 % would lead to unnatural face versions (cf., the “uncanny valley”- effect [41]). Therefore, we decided to apply a smaller size manipulation to the faces. The manipulation of the sizes of the eyes, nose and mouth of each of the faces were identical to the manipulation of the car fronts, although by only 10 % for both enlarging and shrinking (see Figure 2, right side). The faces’ relational characteristics (e.g., distance nose - upper lip, distance between the eyes) were changed as little as possible.

Figure 2: Examples of the Used Stimulus Material

2.3 Participants and Procedure

One group of participants rated the 32 cars ($N = 19$; $M_{\text{age}} = 23$ yrs, $SD_{\text{age}} = 3$ yrs; 74% females) and another group rated the 32 faces ($N = 16$; $M_{\text{age}} = 27$ yrs, $SD_{\text{age}} = 6$ yrs; 75% females) for cuteness on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = “not cute at all” to 7 = “very cute”). As the participants’ task to rate the cars for cuteness was not trivial, in both studies the participants were carefully instructed what cuteness means - especially with respect to cars. We told participants in the car group that, apart from living organisms, consumer products (e.g., *Hello Kitty* products) could also look cute. We were careful to not point out to the physical features that can account for such a look. The stimuli were presented in random order on a high resolution computer screen. Each picture was presented for two seconds in the middle of the screen, then the rating scale appeared and participants were asked to provide their rating. All participants saw both the basic and the manipulated versions, but the pictures were randomized in such a way that the basic and manipulated versions of the same stimulus were never presented in sequence.

3 Results

3.1 Cuteness Perception of Car Fronts (Study 1)

To test our hypothesis that the manipulated, babyfaced cars will be perceived as cuter than the basic, non-manipulated cars, we conducted a paired t -test using the 16 car models as units of analysis. The analysis yielded a significant difference in the perceived cuteness between the babyfaced ($M_{\text{babyface}} = 4.02$, $SD = 1.35$) and non-manipulated versions ($M_{\text{basic}} = 3.52$, $SD = 1.33$), $t(15) = -9.59$, $p < .001$, $d = .38$. The babyfaced versions were perceived as cuter than the basic, non-manipulated versions. At the single stimulus level (difference between basic and manipulated versions calculated separately for the 16 car pairs), the size manipulation effect varied from an average cuteness increase of $\Delta = 0.16$ ($p = .30$, one-sided) to $\Delta = 0.84$ ($p = 0.008$). We also tested the effects of car shape on the cuteness ratings. A 2 (size manipulation: basic vs. babyfaced) \times 2 (car shape: compact vs. medium-class) within-between-subjects ANOVA with repeated measures on the first factor and car shape as between-subjects factor revealed that the cars’ shape had a significant effect on perceived cuteness. There were higher cuteness ratings for compact cars than for medium-class cars ($M_{\text{compact}} = 4.60$, $SD = 1.11$ versus $M_{\text{medium}} =$

2.70, $SD = 0.68$), $F(1, 14) = 15.72$, $p = .001$. The effect of the feature size manipulation was also significant ($F(1, 14) = 86.42$, $p < .001$). Interestingly, there was no interaction effect between feature size manipulation and car shape ($F < 1$; $p = .44$). The latter result suggested that it was not only the cars' segment and explicit preexisting knowledge structures such as "compact cars are cute" that accounted for the perceived cuteness, but that the effect on perceived cuteness was also due to the feature size manipulations according to the baby-schema. Although we found a statistically significant effect of feature size manipulation on perceived cuteness, post-experiment interviews revealed that most of the participants were unaware of these manipulations. Participants only reported some brand association influence (such as "BMW Mini is a cute brand"), but as our analysis showed, even basically very cute cars got cuter due to the baby-schema manipulation (for example, absolute cuteness ratings of BMW Mini increased by 0.5 scale points due to the manipulation).

3.2 Cuteness Perception of Human Faces (Study 2)

To test the hypothesis that people will be more sensitive to baby-schema features in human faces than in car fronts, we applied the same feature size manipulation to human faces and compared the cuteness ratings between the non-manipulated and manipulated faces. As expected, a paired t -test yielded a significant difference in perceived cuteness between the manipulated ($M_{\text{babyface}} = 3.67$, $SD = 0.87$) and non-manipulated faces ($M_{\text{basic}} = 3.14$, $SD = 0.78$), $t(15) = -6.22$, $p < .001$, $d = .64$. The babyfaced versions of the faces were perceived as cuter than the non-manipulated versions. Hence, our manipulations were suited for manipulating perceived cuteness. In comparing Cohen's effect sizes from the two studies, we found that participants' cuteness perceptions were much more sensitive to baby-schema cues in human faces than in car fronts ($d_{\text{cars}} = .38$ versus $d_{\text{faces}} = .64$), which was in accordance with our second hypothesis.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

Applying the theory of innate visual key stimuli, we predicted differences in people's responses to different versions of car designs. In two studies, we found that both car fronts and human faces were perceived as cuter when—in accordance with the baby-schema—the size of the headlights (eyes) was increased, and the size of the grille and air intake (nose and mouth) was decreased. Thus, our results indicate that people are able to detect innate key stimuli in artifacts, which confirms the results of previous studies on face-like product designs. Importantly, our results suggest that people do not only detect visual key stimuli in product designs, but also show affective responses (i.e., cuteness response), that are comparable to innate affective responses, to artifacts possessing such features. However, our results also revealed that visual key stimuli in human faces elicited stronger cuteness responses than cars. Thus, when innate visual patterns such as the baby-schema are generalized onto non-human stimuli, consumers' sensitivity to these cues might be weaker.

Based on our findings, we advice product designers that to elicit strong positive responses in consumers, they should exaggerate the characteristics of visual key stimuli in product designs (e.g., very large headlights that would be unnaturally large as eyes in a human face). In our studies, we focused solely on cars as product category. However, the design concept "cuteness" might be applied to all product categories where a strong consumer-product relationship is part of the marketing strategy, but whose category members have rather a functional than emotional value (e.g., think of electronic devices such as cell phones which could elicit a "protective instinct" in consumers due to a cute appearance). On the other side, cuteness is of course less suitable

for product designs which shall represent brand values such as status or power.

In our study, we requested spontaneous affective responses to product features resembling innate visual key stimuli. In future studies, it might be interesting to take a deeper look at effects of cute product designs on overt behavior. As the baby-schema also triggers behavioral responses such as caretaking, the effect of visual key stimuli on a consumer's willingness to purchase, use and keep a product should be further investigated. Furthermore, cross-cultural effects and sex differences could also be examined to find further evidence that consumers' responses to human-like product designs are shaped by innate perceptual and behavioral mechanisms.

5 References

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